

A Osteology Study on Assimilation of the Atlas Bone in Hyderabad Region

Vijaya Mangalur¹, Praveen Kumar M²

¹Associate Professor, Dept. of Anatomy, Kamineni Medical College Narketpalli

²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Anatomy, Kamineni Medical College Narketpalli

Received: 17-03-2023 / Revised: 21-04-2023 / Accepted: 26-05-2023

Corresponding author: Dr. Vijaya Mangalur

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Introduction: Occipitalization of the atlas is defined as congenital bony fusion of the atlas vertebra to the base of the occipital bone of the skull. It is also known as assimilation of atlas, occipitocervical synostosis or atlantooccipital fusion.

Materials and Methods: A total of 100 adult dried human skulls of unknown sex and age from the department of Anatomy, Kamineni medical college Narketpalli, Hyd, were included in the study.

Results: Out of 100 adult human skulls studied, we observed atlantooccipital assimilation in 2 skulls amounting to 2 %. Each skull was carefully observed for variations. Findings in the skulls with atlantooccipital fusion were as follows.

Conclusion: Occipitalization of atlas is the most common anomaly of the craniocervical junction which can remain asymptomatic for first 2 decades of life.

Keywords: Occipitalization, Atlas.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Occipitalization of the atlas is defined as congenital bony fusion of the atlas vertebra to the base of the occipital bone of the skull. It is also known as assimilation of atlas, occipitocervical syntosis or atlanto-occipital fusion. It is one of the most common osseous anomalies of the craniovertebral junction¹. It was first described by Rokitansky in 1844 and was first demonstrated by Schuller roentgenographically in 1911. It results due to failure of segmentation and separation of the most caudal occipital sclerotome and the first cervical sclerotome during the first few weeks of fetal life. It represents the most cephalic blocked vertebra encountered in the spine. Incidence of atlanto-occipital fusion

ranges from 0.14% to 0.75% of the population with both sexes being equally affected². The aim of the present study was to determine the prevalence of atlanto-occipital fusion along with its brief embryological explanation and clinical implication. Knowledge of this anatomical variation is important for radiologists, neurologists and neurosurgeons.

Materials and Methods:

A total of 100 adult dried human skulls of unknown sex and age from the Department of Anatomy, Kamineni medical college Narketpalli, Hyd, were included in the study. The external and internal surfaces of the entire occipital bone were observed by visual inspection. Appropriate

measurements were taken and the specimens were photographed.

Results

Out of 100 adult human skulls studied, we observed atlanto-occipital assimilation in 2 skulls amounting to 2 %. Each skull was carefully observed for variations. Findings in the skulls with atlanto-occipital fusion were as follows,

Skull 1:

- Partial occipitalization of atlas was found.
- Anterior arch of atlas was partially fused with anterior margin of foramen magnum leaving a slit like gap measuring 16mm transversely between it and the basilar part of occipital bone.
- Superior articular facets of atlas were completely fused with condylar facets of occipital bone.
- Tip of the left transverse process was fused with the tympanic plate of temporal bone leaving a gap between the costotransverse bar and jugular process.
- Both the foramina transversarium were normal in dimension.

- Right posterior arch was complete, and it was fused with the right part of the posterior margin of foramen magnum except for a small foramen on its superior surface close to the transverse process, most probably for the transmission of the right vertebral artery.
- Left posterior arch was incomplete. It extended 15mm from the left inferior articular facet leaving a deficit between it and the posterior arch. A small canal was observed on the superior surface of posterior arch which may have transmitted vertebral artery and the first cervical nerve.
- Dimensions of inferior articular facets were, RIAF was 19mm in length and 14mm in width, LIAF was 17mm in length and 18mm in width.
- Foramen magnum was 33mm in sagittal diameter and 30mm in transverse diameter.
- An articular facet measuring 8mm in width and 6mm in length was found on the posterior surface of anterior arch in the midline for articulation with the odontoid process of axis vertebra was found.

Figure 1: skull showing incomplete assimilation of atlas.

Skull 2:

- Complete occipitalization of atlas was found.
- Anterior arch of atlas was partially fused with anterior margin of foramen magnum except for a small foramen in the midline between it and the basilar part of occipital bone.
- Superior articular facets of atlas were completely fused with condylar facets of occipital bone.
- Tip of the left transverse process was fused with the tympanic plate of temporal bone on the right side leaving a gap between the costotransverse bar and jugular process.
- Posterior arch was complete, and it was fused with the posterior margin of foramen magnum except for a small foramen on its superior surface close to the transverse process on both the sides, most probably for the transmission of vertebral artery and C1 nerve.
- Dimensions of inferior articular facets were, RIAF was 21mm in length and 12mm in width with an extension in the internal margin of foramen magnum with length 13mm and width 7mm, LIAF was 18mm in length and 16mm in width.
- Foramen magnum was 22mm in sagittal diameter and 26mm in transverse diameter.
- No articular facet was found on the posterior surface of anterior arch in the midline for articulation with the odontoid process of axis.

Figure 2: skull showing complete assimilation of atlas.

Discussion

Occipitalization of atlas results due of failure of segmentation and separation of the most caudal occipital sclerotome and the first cervical sclerotome during the first few weeks of fetal life [2]. It is commonly associated with concomitant neurovascular and skeletal anomalies at the craniovertebral junction, which may produce a variety of symptoms [3]. . The patients with craniovertebral joint anomalies exhibit the first neurological

signs and symptoms usually no sooner than the second decade [4]. Absolute immobility of an occipitalized atlantooccipital joint results in compensatory hypermobility between the atlas and axis. Approximately 50% of patients with atlanto-occipital fusion develop atlanto-axial instability [5]. Neurological symptoms associated with occipitalization of the atlas are attributed to the ligamentous laxity of the transverse ligament about the odontoid process

caused by repeated flexion and extension of the neck leading to the compression of the spinal cord or actual indentation of the medulla oblongata [6]. The patient will be probably asymptomatic if the odontoid process is located below the level of foramen magnum. This relationship is best assessed through the use of *McRaes & Barnon (1953)* line which is drawn across the foramen magnum. Normally the odontoid process should not project above this line⁷. Patients with occipitalization of the atlas may have the following physical features: low hairline, torticollis, restricted neck movements and / or abnormal short neck. In neurological examination of the atlanto occipital fusion patient may reveal the following clinical findings: headache, neck pain, numbness and pain in the limbs, weakness, abnormal head posture, posteriorly located dull aching headache. Cranial nerve findings associated with occipitalization of the atlas include tinnitus, visual disturbances and lower cranial nerve palsies leading to dysphagia and dysarthria. [7] The neurological symptoms and signs of atlanto-occipital fusion cannot be distinguished from those of the Arnold Chiari malformation as the pathophysiology of both is essentially the same⁷. Spinal cord compression always occurs when the sagittal spinal canal diameter behind the odontoid process is less than or equal to 14 mm. Cord compression is possible when the sagittal canal diameter is between 15 and 17 mm. And almost never occurs at a distance of 18 mm or more [8]. Gholve et al studied 30 cases of occipitalization of atlas in children with mean age of 6.5yrs and classified it morphologically into 4 zones, zone 1 with fused anterior arch, zone 2 with fused lateral masses, zone 3 with a fused posterior arch and zone 4 with combination of fused zones. They also found 57% of patients had an associated atlantoaxial instability, 26% had an associated C2-C3 fusion, 37% had spinal canal encroachment and the highest prevalence of which was found in zone 2

patients [9]. Lopez et al reported that three patients with atlanto-occipital fusion have had cervical pain and two patients had tonic or clonic convulsions [10]. Iwata et al reported a case of atlanto-occipital fusion with unusual neurological symptoms [11]. Sabuncuoglu H et al. reported a case of hypoplasia of the posterior arch of the C1. They said that upper cervical anomalies can be misinterpreted as fractures, luxation, osteolysis or instability [12].

Conclusion

Occipitalization of atlas is the most common anomaly of the craniocervical junction which can remain asymptomatic for first 2 decades of life. Detection and treatment of this deformity are essential as this deformity often causes cervical spine instability. Special imaging such as CT scan, 3-dimensional CT scan or MRI should be obtained before surgery.

References

1. Hensinger RN. Osseous anomalies of the craniovertebral junction. *Spine*. 1986; 11: 323–333
2. Guebert GM, Yochum TR, Rowe LJ. Congenital anomalies and normal skeleton variants. In: *Essentials of Skeletal Radiology*. Yochum TR, Rowe LJ, eds. Baltimore, Williams & Wilkins. 1987; 197–306.
3. M. Sharma, B. Singh, A. Abhaya and H. Kumar. Occipitalization of atlas with other associated anomalies of skull. *Eur J Anat*, 2008;12 (3): 159-167.
4. Kruyff E. Occipital dysplasia in infancy. The early recognition of craniovertebral abnormalities. *Radiology*. 1965; 85: 501–507
5. Warner WC. Pediatric cervical spine. In: Canale ST Ed. *Campbell's Operative Orthopaedics*, 10th ed. Mosby, St. Louis, 2003; 2: 1736-1737.
6. Jayanthi V., Kulkarni, R.; Kulkarni, R.N. Atlanto - Occipital Fusion –

- Report of Two Cases, J Anat. Soc. India. 2003; 52(1) 71-73.
7. Mc Rae D.L., Barnon A.S. Occipitalization of atlas. American Journal of Roentgenology. 1953; 70: 23 - 45.
 8. Greenbery A.D. Atlanto – axial Dislocation, Brain. 1968; 91:655.
 9. Gholve PA, Hosalkar HS, Ricchetti ET, Pollock AN, Dormans JP, Drummond DS. Occipitalization of the atlas in children. Morphologic classification, associations and clinical relevance. J Bone Joint Surg Am. 2007 Mar; 89(3):571-8.
 10. Loez ZA, Limousin LA, Mantz JR. Contribution a la sistemica las malformation del atlas a la luz de una neuva malformation inestable. Rev. Clin. Espanola. 1964; 94:208-215.
 11. Iwata A, Murata M, Nukina N, Kanazawa.I. Foramen magnum syndrome caused by atlanto occipital assimilation. J. Neurol. Sci. 1998;154: 229-231.
 12. S Hakan, O Selcuk, K Demet, T Erdener. Congenital Hypoplasia of the Posterior Arch of the Atlas: Case.